

Antimicrobial Resistance Pattern of Bacteria Isolated from Chickens in Sokoto Metropolis

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An experimental study was carried out to evaluate the antimicrobial resistance pattern of bacteria isolated from cloacal swab of poultry. A total of 100 cloacal Swabs were taken from chickens in the live birds market and bacteria were isolated on different media using standard microbiological techniques (isolation, phenotypic and biochemical characterization, antimicrobial susceptibility testing). Bacterial isolates were phenotypically identified and recorded. Isolates were sub-cultured and biochemical tests were conducted with each result recorded respectively. A total of 95 bacteria were isolated and identified. The identified bacteria and the rate of occurrence is *Esherichia coli* (69.5%), *Edwardsiella tarda*, *Salmonella spp*, *Pantoea agglomerans* and *Providencia stuartii* (4.2%) respectively. That of *Citrobacter koseri* and *Staphylococcus aureus* is 3.1% respectively and that of *Hafnia alvei*, *Streptococcus spp* and *Citrobacter freundii* is 2.1% respectively while the rate of occurrence of *Proteus spp* is 1.1%. Similarly, some bacteria displayed multidrug resistant traits as seen in high multiple antibiotic resistance (MAR) index obtained. In conclusion, the study revealed various degrees of antimicrobial resistance among bacteria community in chickens in the study area. These underscore the urgent need to enlighten the farmers on the benefits of prudent agricultural use of antimicrobials on food safety and poultry disease management

Keywords: Cloaca, Bacteria, Antimicrobial, Resistance, Susceptibility

INTRODUCTION

Poultry is the term used to describe group of birds kept for meat and egg (e.g chicken) or reared or hunted for a useful purpose (e.g pheasants. The poultry industry in Nigeria can be divided into three main sections: small, medium and large-scale production with 25% being provided by commercial farms, 15% semi-commercial and 60% from backyard (David, 2002).

With increased acceptance of chicken, egg and meat, the demand for these products is ever increasing. The Nigerian poultry industry is estimated at ₦80 billion and is comprised of approximately 165 million birds, which produced 650,000 tonnes of eggs and 300,000 tonnes of poultry meat in 2013 (FAOSTAT, 2018). From a market size perspective, Nigeria's egg production is the largest in Africa and it has the second largest chicken population

after South African's 200 million birds (SAHEL, 2015). Poultry, as an aspect of livestock production outnumbers all other forms of livestock in Nigeria and not surprisingly is found throughout the country (Adeyemo and Onikoyi, 2012).

Despite the leading role of poultry production in the livestock industry of Nigeria, it faces series of challenges which are not over emphasized. High rate of diseases and pest attack as a major challenge in poultry production (Ajala *et al.*, 2007 ;). This remains one of the major threats to poultry production in Nigeria. The major poultry diseases in Nigeria are may include bacterial, viral, fungal and protozoa (Aromolaran *et al.*, 2013). These diseases spread easily during transportation of birds, use of contaminated equipment's among others. Non-infectious causes of immunosuppression (stress, poor nutrition, dust, vitamins and mineral deficiencies and improper use of antibiotics) in poultry production have also been identified (Chitate and Guta, 2001). The aim of

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the study was to assess poultry farmers' knowledge, attitude and practice regarding antimicrobial resistance and study antimicrobial resistance pattern of bacteria isolated from poultry.

Study Area

This study was conducted in Sokoto metropolis, Sokoto state. The state is located in the extreme North-West region of Nigeria near the confluence of the Sokoto and Rima rivers. Located between longitude 4°8E and 6°54E, and latitudes 12°N and 13°58N, the state is bordered in the North by Niger Republic, Zamfara State to the East and Kebbi State to the South and West (NPC, 2006).

In terms of vegetation, the state falls within the savannah zone, which is open Tsetse fly free grassland suitable for cultivation of grain crops and animal husbandry. Sokoto has an annual average temperature of 28.3°(82.9°). Rainfall starts late, from June to October with mean annual fall ranging from 50mm to 1,300mm. From late October to February, the cold season is marked by harmattan wind blowing Sahara dust over the land. Heat is more severe in the State in March and April where temperature is averagely 39°C (Anonymous, 2002).

Sample Collection and Transportation

The cloacal areas of the chickens were cleaned using paper towels. Sterile swab sticks were used to swab the cloaca of 100 birds from live bird market. These samples were placed in an iced cooler and transported immediately to the laboratory for processing.

Culture and Isolation

MacConkey and nutrient media were prepared based on manufacturer instructions, autoclaved at 121°C for 15 minutes and poured into sterile petri dishes. These petri dishes were left on the bench to solidify. All the samples were inoculated on MacConkey and nutrient agar using streak method. These inoculated media were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The colonies observed afterwards were macroscopically examined for colonial characteristics and features such as shape, size, color and consistency. These findings were recorded.

Smear Preparation, Staining and Microscopic Examination of Bacteria Isolated

A drop of distilled water was placed on clean grease free glass slide. A loop full of colony was smeared with the water on the glass slide and allowed to air dry. The slide was fixed by passing over flame. The Gram staining technique was used to stain the slide. This slide was labeled. All other slides were prepared in similar manner. A drop of immersion oil was placed on the prepared slide

and viewed under the microscope at x100 oil immersion objective.

Subculture on Selective/Differential Media

Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) and Xylose lysine deoxycholate (XLD) agar were prepared according to manufacturers' instructions. Prepared agar was autoclaved, poured into sterile petri dishes and left to solidify. The petri dishes were labelled. Using streak method, all samples were inoculated. Plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Colonial morphology of the plates were observed and recorded.

Biochemical Tests

Biochemical media (Citrate agar, Triple Sugar Iron (TSI) agar, MR-VP and Tryptophan broths) were prepared according to manufacturer's instructions. These preparations were distributed into tubes and autoclaved. The first two biochemical media were cooled in slanted positions and after it solidified they were labeled. The tubes were inoculated and incubated at 37°C for 48 hours. Color changes were observed and recorded.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing

The antibiotic susceptibility test of bacterial pathogen isolates was determined by the disk diffusion method. The plates were incubated aerobically at an optimum temperature of 37°C for 24 h. The bacterial species were tested against 13 antibiotics (with their respective concentrations) belonging to seven different classes, namely,

- Quinolones [Ciprofloxacin (10mcg), Ofloxacin(5mcg), Levofloxacin (5mcg)]
- Aminoglycosides [Gentamycin (10mcg), Netilin (30mcg)]
- β -lactams [Penicillins,(Amoxycylav (10mcg), Cloxacillin (1mcg)] and [Cephalosporins, Cephalexin (10mcg), Ceftriaxone (30mcg)]
- Sulfonamides (Co-trimoxazole, 25mcg)
- Lincomycin (Clindamycin, 2mcg)
- Macrolides (Erythromycin, 15mcg)
- Tetracyclines (Tetracycline, 30mcg).

The multiple antibiotic resistances (MAR) index for each isolate was manually calculated using the formula:

$$MAR = \frac{\text{Number of antimicrobials, organism shows resistance}}{\text{Total number of antimicrobials tested}}$$

RESULTS

Out of a total of 100 cloacal swab samples, 95 bacteria were isolated and identified. The rate of occurrence of

Table 1 Different Bacteria Isolated from Cloacal Swabs from Live Bird Market, Sokoto.

Isolates	Frequency	Rate of Occurrence (%)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	66	69.5
<i>Edwardsiella tarda</i>	4	4.2
<i>Citrobacter koseri</i>	3	3.1
<i>Salmonella spp</i>	4	4.2
<i>Hafnia alvei</i>	2	2.1
<i>Pantoea agglomerans</i>	4	4.2
<i>Streptococcus spp</i>	2	2.1
<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	2	2.1
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	3	3.1
<i>Providencia stuartii</i>	4	4.2
<i>Proteus spp</i>	1	1.1
Total	95	99.9

Table 2: Resistance Pattern of Gram-Positive Bacteria to Some Commonly used Antibiotics.

Antibiotic	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (n=4)	<i>Streptococcus spp</i> (n=3)
Amoxyclav(10mcg)	4(100)	1(33.3)
Cefalexin(10mcg)	2(50)	3(100)
Ciprofloxacin(10mcg)	0(0)	0(0)
Clindamycin(2mcg)	2(50)	1(33.3)
Cloxacillin(1mcg)	4(100)	3(100)
Cotrimoxazole(25mcg)	0(0)	0(0)
Erythromycin(15mcg)	0(0)	3(100)
Tetracycline(30mcg)	2(50)	1(33.3)

Escherichia coli is 69.5%, the rate of occurrence of *Edwardsiella tarda*, *Salmonella spp*, *Pantoea agglomerans* and *Providencia stuartii* is 4.2% respectively. The rate of occurrence of *Citrobacter koseri* and *Staphylococcus aureus* is 3.1% respectively. The rate of occurrence of *Hafnia alvei*, *Streptococcus spp* and *Citrobacter freundii* is 2.1% respectively while the rate of occurrence of *Proteus spp* is 1.1% (Table 1). *Staphylococcus aureus* and *streptococcus spp* are susceptible to ciprofloxacin. These two bacteria appear to be susceptible to cotrimoxazole as well. *S. aureus* on the other hand is susceptible to erythromycin while *Streptococcus spp* is resistant to erythromycin. These two gram positive bacteria are resistant to all the other antibiotics tested (Table 4.2).

All the organisms are susceptible to Ofloxacin. *E.coli* is resistant to all the other antibiotics tested. *E. tarda* is susceptible to all the antibiotics tested except tetracycline. *C. koseri* is resistant to other antibiotics tested except ceftriazone. *Salmonella spp* is resistant to Gentamycin, Cotrimoxazole, Netilin, Tetracycline and Amoxyclav. *Proteus spp* is resistant to only Cotrimoxazole and Tetracycline. *C. freundii* is resistant to Amoxyclav, Tetracycline, Cotrimoxazole and Gentamycin. *H. alvei* is resistant to only tetracycline. *P. agglomerans* and *P.stuartii* are resistant to Tetracycline and Cotrimaxazole while being susceptible to other antibiotics tested (Table 3).

Each organism and its multiple antibiotic resistance (MAR) index. Based on this index, *E. coli*, *C. freundii*, *C.*

koseri, *Salmonella spp*, *S. aureus*, *Streptococcus spp*, *Proteus spp*, *P. agglomerans* are all multi antimicrobial resistant in nature. *E. tarda*, *H. alvei* and *P. stuartii* are not multi antimicrobial resistant (Table 4).

The use of antimicrobials in poultry farms has been widely reported to be a major problem (Ejeh *et al.*, 2017). This is true as far as this study is concerned as eleven bacterial organisms were identified. From the results of the present study, *E. coli* had a significantly high rate of occurrence (69.5%), giving a wide margin compared to the other organisms isolated. Similar study in Maiduguri, Nigeria have reported different rate of occurrence of 38.9% for *E. coli* from chicken (Mamza *et al.*, 2010). The high occurrence of *E. coli* in this study could be linked to a lack of good sanitary conditions and lack of good farm management by individuals who have little education and experience in poultry farm practices as have previously been documented (Saliu *et al.*, 2012). The highest resistance from AmoxyClav in this study is similar with the report of Kwoji *et al.* (2019). The present study has observed a MAR index for *E. coli* isolates to have a value greater than 0.2 which differ from the study by Tama *et al.* (2019), where he reported isolates with MAR index of less than 0.2.

The extent of resistance observed from the antimicrobial susceptibility by *E. coli*, explains the reason for its high rate of occurrence. *E. coli* has shown the most resistance to the antimicrobials tested. Of all the organisms isolated, *E. coli*, *C. freundii*, *C. koseri*, *Salmonella spp*, *P. agglomerans*, *S. aureus*,

Table 3: Resistance Pattern of Gram-Negative Bacteria to Some Commonly used Antibiotics

Antibiotic	<i>E. coli</i> (n=24)	<i>E. tarda</i> (n=1)	<i>C. koseri</i> (n=4)	<i>Salmonella</i> <i>spp</i> (n=2)	<i>Proteus spp</i> (n=1)	<i>C. fruendii</i> (n=8)	<i>P. agglomerans</i> (n=1)	<i>P. stuartii</i> (n=1)	<i>H. alvei</i> (n=1)
Ceftriaxone(30mcg)	7(29.2)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
Gentamycin(10mcg)	10(41.60)	0(0)	3(75)	1(50)	0(0)	5(62.5)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
Cotrimoxazole(25mcg)	12(50)	0(0)	3(75)	2(100)	1(100)	5(62.5)	1(100)	1(100)	0(0)
Levofloxacin(5mcg)	3(12.5)	0(0)	1(25)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
Netilin(30mcg)	4(16.6)	0(0)	1(25)	1(50)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
Tetracycline(30mcg)	8(33.3)	1(100)	3(75)	1(50)	1(100)	3(37.5)	1(100)	0(0)	1(100)
Amoxyclav(30mcg)	15(62.5)	0(0)	4(100)	1(50)	0(0)	3(37.5)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
Ofloxacin(5mcg)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)

Table 4: Some bacterial Isolates and their Multi Antimicrobial Resistance (MAR) Index.

Organisms	MAR index
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	0.875
<i>Citrobacter fruendii</i>	0.5
<i>Citrobacter koseri</i>	0.75
<i>Salmonella spp</i>	0.625
<i>Streptococcus spp</i>	0.75
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	0.625
<i>Edwardsiellatarda</i>	0.125
<i>Proteus spp</i>	0.25
<i>Hafnia alvei</i>	0.125
<i>Pantoeaagglomerans</i>	0.25
<i>Providencia stuartii</i>	0.125

Streptococcus spp and *Proteus spp* showed varying levels of multiple antimicrobial resistance (CLSI, 2015). Ciprofloxacin and ofloxacin which are fluoroquinolones happens to exhibit highest potency of importance. All organism isolated were susceptible to these antimicrobials. Cotrimoxazole shows potency against all gram-positive bacteria tested but to a few of the gram-negative bacteria tested. Most of the organisms have shown resistance to tetracycline. This may be due to the constant abuse and usage of tetracyclines as they are readily available and affordable as previously established (Rotchell and Paul, 2016).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study revealed various degrees of antimicrobial resistance

among bacteria community in chickens in the study area. These underscore the urgent need to enlighten the farmers on the benefits of prudent agricultural use of antimicrobials on food safety and poultry disease management. It study is therefore recommended the Imprudent use of antimicrobials among farmers and also reiterates the needs for discontinuation of sale of essential antimicrobial as over the counter drugs.

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